

D4.9. Demonstration products produced delivered to industrial end users for market test

Acronym	Pro-Enrich		
Title	“Demonstration products produced and delivered to industrial end users for market test”		
Grant agreement number	792050		
Call	H2020-BBI-JTI-2017 (BIO BASED INDUSTRIES PPP)		
Project coordinator	Danish Technological Institute (DTI)		
Topic	BBI.2017.R4		
Type of action	BBI-RIA		
Document Type (R/DEM/DEC/OTHER)	DEM _ Demonstrator		
Dissemination Level (PU/CO/CI)	PU _ Public		
Leading partner	Natac		
Contributing partners	Natac, DTI, Bangor University.		
Due date of delivery	M39	Submission date	28.07.2021
		Resubmission date	05-03-2022

Disclaimer and acknowledgements

“This project has received funding from the Bio Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 792050”

This document reflects the views of the author(s) and does not necessarily reflect the views or policy of the European Commission. Whilst efforts have been made to ensure the accuracy and completeness of this document, the BBI-JU shall not be liable for any errors or omissions, however caused.

Document information

Document history			
Issue	Date	Comment	Lead author
1.0	23.04.2020	1 st Draft	Alba Ramos Scientific Researcher Natac Biotech SL aramos@natacgroup.com
2.0	03.03.2022	1 st revision	Alba Ramos Scientific Researcher Natac Biotech SL aramos@natacgroup.com

Additional author(s) and contribution	
Name	Organisation
José M ^a Pinilla jmpinilla @natacgroup.com	Natac Biotech SL
Angelica Tamayo Tenorio ante@teknologisk.dk	Danish Technological Institute
Marcel Tutor Ale male@dti.dk	Danish Technological Institute (DTI)
Paul Baker Paul.baker@bangor.ac.uk	Bangor University

Approved by:			
Issue	Date	Name	Organisation
2.0	05.03.2022	Anne Christine Steenkjær Hastrup acha@teknologisk.dk	Danish Technological Institute
2.0	03.03.2022	Natanya Majbritt Louie Hansen nmlh@teknologisk.dk	Danish Technological Institute

Contents

1. INTRODUCTION.....	5
2. PRODUCTS OBTAINED FROM TOMATOES	6
3. PRODUCTS OBTAINED FROM CITRUS	11
4. PRODUCTS OBTAINED FROM RAPE SEEDS	15
5. CONCLUSIONS.....	23

Executive summary

This deliverable summarizes the final products produced and delivered to industrial end users for market test based on feed stocks of rapeseeds, tomatoes, and citrus fruits.

1. INTRODUCTION

During the Pro-Enrich project, different biorefinery processes have been developed from feedstocks of olives, rapeseeds, tomatoes and citrus fruits. Some of these processes have led to several Pro-Enrich products that are being tested in formulated market products by end users. The objective of this deliverable is to provide an overview of products produced and delivered to industrial end users for market test based on feedstocks of rapeseeds, tomatoes and citrus fruits. Some of the products described here were previously reported in D4.2. and have been updated in this deliverable. The following table features a summary of all the samples produced by each partner involved. The testing of samples is reported in D5.6 *Final performance assessment report all end users* due in M35.

Sample name	Raw material	Partner	Amount
Carotenoids-rich tomato oleoresin	Cherry tomatoes	Natac	20 g
Carotenoids-rich tomato powder	Cherry tomatoes	Natac	50 g
Protein hydrolysate from tomato seeds	Tomato pomace	BU	40 g
Citrus, dry extract, 60% Hesperidin	Orange peel	Natac	300 g
Citrus, dry extract, 90% Hesperidin	Orange peel	Natac	300 g
Protein extract from hot-pressed rapeseed cake (batch 1)	Rapeseed	DTI	5 kg
Protein extract from hot-pressed rapeseed cake (batch 2)	Rapeseed	DTI	5 kg
Protein extract from cold-pressed rapeseed cake (batch 4)	Rapeseed	DTI	0.1 kg
Protein extract from cold-pressed rapeseed cake (batch 5)	Rapeseed	DTI	0.5 kg
Protein extract from cold-pressed rapeseed cake (batch 8)	Rapeseed	DTI	1 kg
Protein extract from cold-pressed rapeseed cake (batch 11)	Rapeseed	DTI	1 kg
Protein extract from cold-pressed rapeseed cake (batch 16)	Rapeseed	DTI	0.7 kg
Protein extract from hot-pressed rapeseed cake (batch 17)	Rapeseed	DTI	5.5 kg

2. PRODUCTS OBTAINED FROM TOMATOES

PRODUCT SPECIFICATIONS

Product: CAROTENOIDS-RICH TOMATO OLEORESIN

Product Code: NTPRL01

Botanical name: *Solanum lycopersicum*

Plant Part Used: Fruit (Pomace)

Description: Dark-red oily extract

Observations: Extraction of cherry tomato pomace with 2-MeTHF, filtration, concentration and vacuum drying

ANALYSIS	SPECIFICATION	METHODS
Assay (%)	Min 5,0 Lycopene	HPLC
Assay (%)	Min 7,0 Total carotenoids	Internal method
Loss on drying (%)	≤ 5,0	Eu. Pharm c.v. (2.8.17)
Microbiology		
TAMC (cfu/g)	≤ 10000	Eu. Pharm c.v. (2.6.12)
TYMC (cfu/g)	≤ 100	Eu. Pharm c.v. (2.6.12)
Bile-tolerant gram-negative bacteria (cfu/g)	≤ 100	Eu. Pharm c.v. (2.6.31)
Escherichia coli (1 g)	Absence	Eu. Pharm c.v. (2.6.31)
Salmonella (25 g)	Absence	Eu. Pharm c.v. (2.6.31)
Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) *		
Benzo(a)pyrene (ppb)	≤10,0	GC-MS
PAH4 (Sum of (benzo(a)pyrene, benz(a)anthracene, benzo(b)fluoranthene and chrysene (ppb)	≤ 50,0	GC-MS
Heavy metals*		
Lead (ppm)	≤ 3,0	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.4.27)
Arsenic (ppm)	≤ 2,0	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.4.27)
Mercury (ppm)	≤ 0,1	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.4.27)
Cadmium (ppm)	≤ 1,0	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.4.27)
Pesticides*	According to Regulation (EC) N ^o 396/2005 and amendments	SANTE/12682/2019

Storage: Store at 4°C in the dark

Country of origin: Spain

Observations: Unlikely to be hazardous although tests have not been performed; unlikely to be hazardous to the environment

Specification version: 000

This document is computed printed and therefore without signature.

The information set out in this specification and/or in any other document provided with the products does not constitute any warranty other than conformity to the current product specifications. The authorized uses of our products are not the same in all countries and it is your responsibility to verify that the use/s for which they are intended and their labelling are in accordance with current local or national legislation and regulations. The buyer agrees to hold the seller harmless against any third-party claim that it brings cause of unauthorized use of the product and/or its incorrect labelling.

Figure 1. Carotenoids-rich tomato oleoresin.

PRODUCT SPECIFICATIONS

Product: CAROTENOIDS-RICH TOMATO POWDER

Product Code: NTPRL02

Botanical name: *Solanum lycopersicum*

Plant Part Used: Fruit (Pomace)

Description: Dark-orange powder

Observations: Extraction of cherry tomato pomace with 2-MeTHF, filtration, concentration and vacuum drying. Addition of drying agent, milled and sieved

ANALYSIS	SPECIFICATION	METHODS
Assay (%)	Min 1,0 Lycopene	HPLC
Assay (%)	Min 1,5 Total carotenoids	Internal method
Loss on drying (%)	≤ 5,0	Eu. Pharm c.v. (2.8.17)
Bulk density (g/ml)	≥ 0,3	Eu. Pharm c.v. (2.9.34)
Particle size (%)	Min 90% < 250 µm	Eu. Pharm c.v. (2.9.12)
Microbiology		
TAMC (cfu/g)	≤ 10000	Eu. Pharm c.v. (2.6.12)
TYMC (cfu/g)	≤ 100	Eu. Pharm c.v. (2.6.12)
Bile-tolerant gram-negative bacteria (cfu/g)	≤ 100	Eu. Pharm c.v. (2.6.31)
Escherichia coli (1 g)	Absence	Eu. Pharm c.v. (2.6.31)
Salmonella (25 g)	Absence	Eu. Pharm c.v. (2.6.31)
Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) *		
Benzo(a)pyrene (ppb)	≤10,0	GC-MS
PAH4 (Sum of (benzo(a)pyrene, benz(a)anthracene, benzo(b)fluoranthene and chrysene (ppb)	≤ 50,0	GC-MS
Heavy metals*		
Lead (ppm)	≤ 3,0	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.4.27)
Arsenic (ppm)	≤ 2,0	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.4.27)
Mercury (ppm)	≤ 0,1	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.4.27)
Cadmium (ppm)	≤ 1,0	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.4.27)
Pesticides*	According to Regulation (EC) N ^o 396/2005 and amendments	SANTE/12682/2019

Storage: Store at 4°C in the dark

Country of origin: Spain

Observations: Unlikely to be hazardous although tests have not been performed; unlikely to be hazardous to the environment

Specification version: 000

This document is computed printed and therefore without signature.

The information set out in this specification and/or in any other document provided with the products does not constitute any warranty other than conformity to the current product specifications. The authorized uses of our products are not the

Figure 2. Carotenoids-rich tomato powder.

Technical Data Sheet			
1. Sample ref.	BU34.21	2. Date of sampling	29.6.2021
3. Sample name	Protein hydrolysate from tomato seeds		
4. Plant origin	Tomato pomace after removing juice (50 kg) - supplied frozen from Agrofusion		
5. Country of origin	Ukraine		
6. Processing	Sedimentation of seeds and skimming off peel and pulp on surface. High shear mixing of seeds and hydrolysis with Neutrase at neutral pH, centrifugation and rotary evaporation.		
7. Appearance	Pale yellow powder	5. Quantity	40 g
8. Ingredients	Protein content 35.9%		
9. Hazards	Unlikely to be hazardous although tests have not been performed; unlikely to be hazardous to the environment		
10. Storage	Keep dry at room temperature		
11. Comments	Crude protein hydrolysate from tomato seeds for testing by end-users of the consortium. <div style="text-align: center;"> </div>		

3. PRODUCTS OBTAINED FROM CITRUS

PRODUCT SPECIFICATIONS

Product: CITRUS, DRY EXTRACT, 60% HESPERIDIN

Product Code: N202114901

Botanical name: *Citrus sp.*

Plant Part Used: Fruit (Peel)

Description: Yellowish-brown powder with characteristic odor and taste

Observations: Extraction of citrus peels with water (pH 11.5, Ca(OH)₂). Clarification and acidification to pH 4.5 to precipitate the hesperidin. The extract was dried, milled and sieved.

ANALYSIS	SPECIFICATION	METHODS
Assay (%)	Min. 60,0 Hesperidin	HPLC
Loss on drying (%)	≤ 5,0	Eu. Pharm c.v. (2.8.17)
Bulk density (g/ml)	≥ 0,3	Eu. Pharm c.v. (2.9.34)
Particle size (%)	Min 95% < 250 microns	Eu. Pharm c.v. (2.9.12)
Residual solvents		
Ethanol (ppm)	< 5000	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.4.24)
Microbiology		
TAMC (cfu/g)	≤ 10000	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.6.12)
TYMC (cfu/g)	≤ 100	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.6.12)
Bile-tolerant gram-negative bacteria (cfu/g)	≤ 100	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.6.31)
Escherichia coli (1 g)	Absence	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.6.31)
Salmonella (25 g)	Absence	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.6.31)
Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) *		
Benzo(a)pyrene (ppb)	≤ 10	GC - MS
PAH4 (Sum of (benzo(a)pyrene, benz(a)anthracene, benzo(b)fluoranthene and chrysene (ppb)	≤ 50	GC-MS
Heavy metals*		
Lead (ppm)	≤ 3,0	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.4.27)
Arsenic (ppm)	≤ 1,0	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.4.27)
Mercury (ppm)	≤ 0,1	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.4.27)
Cadmium (ppm)	≤ 1,0	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.4.27)
Pesticides*	According to Regulation (EC) N ^o 396/2005 and amendments	SANTE/12682/2019

Storage: Keep dry at room temperature

Country of origin: Spain

Observations: The product is not considered a hazardous material according to GHS (Global Harmonized System) and doesn't fall under Regulation (EC) 1272/2008 and CFR 1910.1200

Specification version: 000

Figure 3. Citrus, dry extract, 60% Hesperidin.

PRODUCT SPECIFICATIONS

Product: CITRUS, DRY EXTRACT, 90% HESPERIDIN

Product Code: N21008403

Botanical name: *Citrus sp.*

Plant Part Used: Fruit (Peel)

Description: Yellowish-brown powder with characteristic odor and taste

Observations: Extraction of citrus peels with water (pH 11.5, Ca(OH)₂). Clarification and acidification to pH 4.5 to precipitate the hesperidin. Dissolution of the precipitate in water (pH 12.0) and recrystallization (pH 4.7). Drying, milling and sieving.

ANALYSIS	SPECIFICATION	METHODS
Assay (%)	Min. 90,0 Hesperidin	HPLC
Loss on drying (%)	≤ 5,0	Eu. Pharm c.v. (2.8.17)
Bulk density (g/ml)	≥ 0,3	Eu. Pharm c.v. (2.9.34)
Particle size (%)	Min 95% < 250 microns	Eu. Pharm c.v. (2.9.12)
Residual solvents		
Ethanol (ppm)	< 5000	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.4.24)
Microbiology		
TAMC (cfu/g)	≤ 10000	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.6.12)
TYMC (cfu/g)	≤ 100	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.6.12)
Bile-tolerant gram-negative bacteria (cfu/g)	≤ 100	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.6.31)
Escherichia coli (1 g)	Absence	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.6.31)
Salmonella (25 g)	Absence	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.6.31)
Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) *		
Benzo(a)pyrene (ppb)	≤ 10	GC - MS
PAH4 (Sum of (benzo(a)pyrene, benz(a)anthracene, benzo(b)fluoranthene and chrysene (ppb)	≤ 50	GC-MS
Heavy metals*		
Lead (ppm)	≤ 3,0	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.4.27)
Arsenic (ppm)	≤ 1,0	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.4.27)
Mercury (ppm)	≤ 0,1	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.4.27)
Cadmium (ppm)	≤ 1,0	Eu. Pharm. v.v. (2.4.27)
Pesticides*	According to Regulation (EC) N ^o 396/2005 and amendments	SANTE/12682/2019

Storage: Keep dry at room temperature

Country of origin: Spain

Observations: The product is not considered a hazardous material according to GHS (Global Harmonized System) and doesn't fall under Regulation (EC) 1272/2008 and CFR 1910 1200

Specification version: 003

Figure 4. Citrus, dry extract, 90% Hesperidin.

4. PRODUCTS OBTAINED FROM RAPE SEEDS

Technical Data Sheet (updated from D4.2)			
1. Sample ref.	Pro-Enrich; demo batch no. 01; sample no. 4-1	2. Date of sampling	02/2019
3. Sample name	Protein extract from hot-pressed rapeseed cake		
4. Appearance	Light yellow very fine powder Pleasant smell	5. Quantity	5 kg
6. Ingredients	Lignocellulose: Protein, sugars, dietary fibers, organic acids, phenols, lipids Protein: 29.5 %		
7. Hazards	Inhalation may cause allergic reaction; unhazardous to the environment		
8. Storage	Keep dry at room temperature		
9. Comments	Protein extract from hot pressed rapeseed cake for demonstration and testing by end-users of the consortium.		

Technical Data Sheet (updated from D4.2)			
1. Sample ref.	Pro-Enrich; demo batch no. 02; sample no. 4-2	2. Date of sampling	02/2019
3. Sample name	Protein extract from hot-pressed rapeseed cake		
4. Appearance	Light yellow very fine powder Pleasant smell	5. Quantity	5 kg
6. Ingredients	Lignocellulose: Protein, sugars, dietary fibres, organic acids, phenols, lipids Protein: 26.7 %		
7. Hazards	Inhalation may cause allergic reaction; unharzardous to the environment		
8. Storage	Keep dry at room temperature		
9. Comments	Protein extract from hot pressed rapeseed cake for demonstration and testing by end-users of the consortium. <div style="text-align: center;"> </div>		

Technical Data Sheet			
1. Sample ref.	Pro-Enrich; demo batch no. 04; sample no. 4-1	2. Date of sampling	04/2019
3. Sample name	Protein extract from cold-pressed rapeseed cake		
4. Appearance	Dark yellow very fine powder Pleasant smell	5. Quantity	0.1 kg
6. Ingredients	Lignocellulose: Protein, sugars, dietary fibres, organic acids, phenols, lipids Protein: data not available		
7. Hazards	Inhalation may cause allergic reaction; unharzardous to the environment		
8. Storage	Keep dry at room temperature		
9. Comments	Protein extract from hot pressed rapeseed cake for demonstration and testing by end-users of the consortium.		

Technical Data Sheet			
1. Sample ref.	Pro-Enrich; demo batch no.05; sample no. 4-1	2. Date of sampling	06/2019
3. Sample name	Protein concentrate from cold-pressed rapeseed cake		
4. Appearance	Dark yellow very fine powder Pleasant smell	5. Quantity	0.5 kg
6. Ingredients	Lignocellulose: Protein, sugars, dietary fibres, organic acids, phenols, lipids, tannin Protein: 56.6 %		
7. Hazards	Inhalation may cause allergic reaction; unharzardous to the environment		
8. Storage	Keep dry at room temperature		
9. Comments	Protein isolate from cold pressed rapeseed cake for demonstration and testing by end-users of the consortium.		

Technical Data Sheet			
1. Sample ref.	Pro-Enrich; demo batch no. 08; sample no. S011	2. Date of sampling	05/2020
3. Sample name	Protein concentrate from cold-pressed rapeseed cake		
4. Appearance	Light yellow very fine powder	5. Quantity	1 kg
6. Ingredients	Lignocellulose: Protein, sugars, dietary fibres, organic acids, phenols, lipids, tannin Protein: 70.8 % Lipid: 0.3 %		
7. Hazards	Inhalation may cause allergic reaction; un Hazardous to the environment		
8. Storage	Keep dry at room temperature		
9. Comments	Protein concentrate from cold pressed rapeseed cake for demonstration and testing by end-users of the consortium.		

Technical Data Sheet			
1. Sample ref.	Pro-Enrich; demo batch no. 11; sample no. S010	2. Date of sampling	03/2020
3. Sample name	Protein isolate from cold-pressed rapeseed cake		
4. Appearance	Light yellow very fine powder	5. Quantity	1 kg
6. Ingredients	Lignocellulose: Protein, sugars, dietary fibres, organic acids, phenols, lipids, tannin Protein: 91.8 % Lipids: <0.3 % Sugars: 3 - 4% Ash: 3 - 4 %		
7. Hazards	Inhalation may cause allergic reaction; unhazardous to the environment		
8. Storage	Keep dry at room temperature		
9. Comments	Protein isolate from cold-pressed rapeseed cake for demonstration and testing by end-users of the consortium. <div style="text-align: center;"> </div>		

Technical Data Sheet			
1. Sample ref.	Pro-Enrich; demo batch no. 16; sample no. S011	2. Date of sampling	07/2021
3. Sample name	Protein extract from cold-pressed rapeseed cake		
4. Appearance	Light yellow very fine powder Sticky during handling Pleasant smell	5. Quantity	0.7 kg
6. Ingredients	Lignocellulose: Protein, sugars, dietary fibres, organic acids, phenols, lipids, tannin Protein: 30 % (preliminary results)		
7. Hazards	Inhalation may cause allergic reaction; un Hazardous to the environment		
8. Storage	Keep dry at room temperature		
9. Comments	Protein extract from cold-pressed rapeseed cake for demonstration and testing by end-users of the consortium.		

Technical Data Sheet			
1. Sample ref.	Pro-Enrich; demo batch no. 17; sample no. S016	2. Date of sampling	07/2021
3. Sample name	Protein concentrate from hot-pressed rapeseed cake		
4. Appearance	Dark yellow very fine powder Pleasant smell	5. Quantity	5.5 kg
6. Ingredients	Lignocellulose: Protein, sugars, dietary fibres, organic acids, phenols, lipids Protein: 72.8 %		
7. Hazards	Inhalation may cause allergic reaction; un Hazardous to the environment		
8. Storage	Keep dry at room temperature		
9. Comments	Protein concentrate from hot pressed rapeseed cake for demonstration and testing by end-users of the consortium.		

5. CONCLUSIONS

Several products have been successfully extracted by partners Danish Technological Institute, Natac and Bangor University. The functionality of the products is being tested by end users for specific applications: pet food, food, adhesives and/or cosmetics.